

Probing the Effectiveness of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) In Improving the Reading Skills of Grade 12 Students

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Index Terms:

concept oriented reading instruction, reading skills, reading performance of grade 12 students

Abstract. The main purpose of this study is to probe the effectiveness of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) in Improving the Reading comprehension Skills of Grade 12 Students of Paliparan II Integrated High School in response to the alarming performance of the senior high school students in reading following the effect of distance learning. The researcher employed quasi-experimental research with one group pre-test and post-test design. More so, there is no controlled group involved in the study. The pretest result served as the baseline in the identification of the respondents involved in the study. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the students in the writing test after the utilization of the Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI). The Z-test also revealed that the performance of the students in the reading test were identical prior to the implementation of the reading strategy. In addition, there is an increment in performance of the students as shown in the learning gains as supported on the theme emerged during the interview among the students. Furthermore, the study disclosed that teaching reading is best done through a variety of strategies and concepts taught together. This approach in teaching reading integrates reading instruction in the classroom and conceptual scientific knowledge with support of student motivation to read, not only fiction books but also information-based literature. CORI has also strengthened reading engagement as, the interplay of motivation, conceptual knowledge, strategies, and social interaction during reading activities. This supports the claim of plethora of research that the Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) is deemed effective in enhancing the reading comprehension skills of the students.

Introduction

Language is the very essence of our humanity and very essential as effective tool for socialization. As individuals or members of a social group, the ability to perform effectively and efficiently in almost all spheres of life depends fundamentally on language skills. Nowadays, most of the senior high school students carry the burden of such a great expectation most specially to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills to navigate and succeed in an increasingly globalized, demanding, and changing environment. One of these challenges is to maintain a high level of competence and confidence in using English. The ability to communicate clearly, effectively, and efficiently in various context and circumstances form the foundation of modern life. Thus, students who cannot read and comprehend definitely fail to assimilate indispensable concepts and resulted to score poorly on tests across disciplines. Reading skills allow students to seek out information, explore subjects in-depth and gain a deeper understanding of the world around them. Several studies had been conducted particularly in reading and skills however until now the root cause is still unidentified. Thus, it becomes a perennial problem for most of educators.

Reading comprehension is ubiquitously one of the utmost problems of English teachers nowadays. This problem can be associated with the poor reading engagement of the students which is evident in the deterioration of their performance during activities that require comprehension. Comprehension is constructing meaning from the printed material (Wilma, 2000). This insinuates that it requires interactive process that uses prior knowledge in combination with the printed

material. The creation of meaning is based on how the reader grasp the message that can be implicitly and explicitly stated. In addition, comprehension is a process of building a connection between what the readers knows and what he or she doesn't know, hence, it is an involving process, often beginning before a book is opened, changing as the material is read, and continuing to change even after the book is completed.

Reading is the true backbone of most learning. Everything starts with the written word — whether it is Mathematics, Science or even Home Economics. As students go up the educational ladder, more reading is usually required as subjects become denser and challenging. (Philippine Star, 2010). Good reading comprehension skills do more than allow students to make sense of what they read. By using higher order thinking skills, they can use new information to help understand of their world through analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. One of the goals of reading is to make new connections to life and to the world. Readers who can use higher order thinking not only show knowledge and understanding of the text, but they can put the information in new context and form relation between ideas.

In one of the focus group discussion of teachers in Paliparan II Integrated High School, it was highlighted that poor performance of students in Mathematics specifically in solving word problem is associated with reading comprehension similar problem exist as experienced among Science Teachers in Teaching Computations and in other learning areas. Some of students probably find it difficult to comprehend or make meaning because they lack the following the repertoire of comprehension strategies, background knowledge of the content, knowledge of the structures and features of the text and the purpose for engaging with the text. This implies that reading comprehension is the utmost problem of teachers not just reading teachers.

Moreover, English teachers share common observation during their English classes that whenever the lesson is on reading, some of the students could hardly answer simple questions such as noting details which concern on the literal questions that can be found in the text and are directly stated. Most of them could not even make inferences about things not directly stated in the text. Others have difficulty recalling previous knowledge which they can make use to increase their reading comprehension. The importance of comprehension skills development as a primordial concern of every English teacher cannot be refuted, underestimated, or undervalued. Having and developing the ability to read accurately and comprehensively and processing other skills with the right attitude and taste indeed of great importance today. Abon (2018) asserted that reading is important in everyday life for it developed ones' ability to think and reason out. Smith (2019) posited similar point of view of the fundamental goal of reading when he said that associating printed words with their meaning causes the reader to think and interact based on his experience.

It can also be noted that in 2018 when the result of Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) was released the Philippines scored the lowest in reading comprehension and the second lowest in Mathematics and Science. With the poor PISA results, DepEd recognizes the urgency of addressing issues and gaps in attaining the quality of basic education in the Philippines. Likewise in the data from the Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEA-PLM) 2019 showed the percentage of Grade 5 Filipino students who achieved minimum proficiency in reading, writing and mathematics was significantly lower than Vietnam and Malaysia. Fifth graders in the Philippines were at par or sometimes even worse than those in Cambodia but performed slightly better than those in Laos and Myanmar. This implies that Grade school students in the Philippines are lagging counterparts in Southeast Asia in reading, math and writing as the study reveals.

Furthermore, in the study of Damasali (2021) on Reading Performance of Senior High School students, he concluded that modular learning has immensely affected the reading comprehension of students. In his study, he assessed the students by giving short reading materials and multiple-choice questions to determine the performance of the students in reading and the result shown that most of the students did not meet the expectation. Identical result from the study of Basco (2020) that he recommended to employ a 21st Learning strategy to address the poor performance of students in reading comprehension. He also, claimed that pandemic has been a contributing factor on why the students cannot even process a literal question. In view of the foregoing problem, the researcher will be employing a strategy to help the struggling learners in Reading at Paliparan II Integrated High School.

The constant quest of teachers for strategies to help address the gaps in the acquisition of learning and to solve problems in reading comprehension among senior high school students in Paliparan II, the researcher proposes a reading strategy which is suitable to make teaching and learning become more effective. There are some strategies and methods in teaching reading, however in this research, CORI Concept-Oriented Reading Instruction strategy will be used to help the teacher to solve the obstacles in reading. It is because Concept-Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) is a reading comprehension instructional program that can involve students in reading, understand the text better, and motivate students to read. In addition, the utilization of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction is to increment the performance of students in reading comprehension.

This approach in teaching reading comes as a curriculum-based strategy that integrates reading instruction in the classroom and conceptual scientific knowledge with support of student motivation to read, not only fiction books but also information-based literature. As claimed by Guthrie (2015), Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) is based on the belief that reading skills can be developed through a variety of strategies and concepts taught together. More specifically, it is a teaching method that defines reading engagement as, “the interplay of motivation, conceptual knowledge, strategies, and social interaction during literacy activities. [...] engagement in reading is crucial for the development of life-long literacy learners”. Moreover, it is likewise described as a program that is designed to foster reading engagement and comprehension through the teaching of reading strategies, teaching of scientific concepts and inquiry skills, and its explicit support of the development of student intrinsic motivation to read. The definition implies and places comprehension and engagement as essential properties for fostering reading as a lifelong skill and practice. These longitudinal skills can be fostered by implementing effective strategies in the classroom (National Reading Panel, 2000). Lastly, it is indispensable to note that comprehension is a developmental skill in describing idea which is begun by the word level and proceeding to attach meaning to an entire reading selection (Kintsch, Rawson, Snowling, and Hulme, 2005). According to Seyed et al (2010), the word comprehension refers to “the ability to go beyond the words, to understand the ideas conveyed in the entire text”.

Statement of the Problem

The main purpose of this study is to probe the effectiveness of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) in Improving the Reading Skills of Grade 12 Students

Broad Question: How does the use of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) in Improving the Reading Skills of Grade 12 Students

Specific questions:

1. What are the pretest and posttest mean performance of the intervention group?
2. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean results of the intervention exposed in the Concept Oriented Reading Instruction?
3. What is the gain score difference from the pretest and posttest scores of the intervention group exposed to using the Concept Oriented Reading Instruction?
4. How do the students perceive the use of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction approach?

Methodology

The participants of the study were the grade 12 students enrolled in Reading and Writing Subject this school year 2023-2024. They were selected purposively based on the parameters enclosed in the selection process such as those whose scores were described as did not meet expectation in the pre-measured reading test. The group of students with poor performance in the pretest as well as those with low grades in Reading and Writing were included in the intervention group.

Data Gathering Methods

The researcher crafted a table of specification where the learning competencies to be measured should be aligned in the K12 curriculum. Lessons covered in the final semester were carefully checked then design a multiple-choice type of test for reading and formulated four questions from different content area that are based on the competencies. The reading test consists of text which was lifted from different content areas in the senior high school core subjects. Furthermore, the researcher prepared Post-test which contained reading test after the full implementation and integration of the Concept Oriented Reading Instruction in the lesson plan to the students. The test was administered to the student-participants after securing permission from the concerned authorities. Moreover, after the preparation all the instruments needed for the study, the researcher consulted subject experts to validate the test questionnaire, lesson plans and the rubric, whether it jibes and answer the research questions of the study. After the validation, all the comments and suggestions were incorporated for the enhancement of the tool.

Lastly, to administer the study, permission will be sought from the school head and once granted, the administration of the test will be done personally by the researcher to ensure 100 percent turnout of retrieval. The test was done by distributing the questionnaires to the students then asking them to answer each question. In addition, the researcher will set time for the students to answer the reading test. The implementation was done through amalgamating the approach in teaching reading. The researcher integrated content from other field of discipline to extract the lessons taught in the target skills to be developed. The use of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction served as reading promoter thus all activities and discussions are revolved around the utilization of the content.

Data Analysis Plan

The gathered data were organized, tabulated, and subjected to statistical treatment to draw facts and decode important findings necessary to substantiate the results of the research. The generated outputs were appended. To answer specific questions raised in the research question, the following statistics formula were used:

Mean: This was used in the study to quantitatively describe the pre-test and post-test performance of the respondents in reading and writing. The numerical values were interpreted based on the scale as followed:

$$X = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

Where: \bar{x} = weighted mean

$\sum fx/n$ = the sum of all the products of f and x, being the frequency of each weight and x as the weight of each operation.

n = total number of respondents

SCORES	VERBAL DESCRIPTIONS
23 – 30	Outstanding
19 – 22	Very satisfactory
15 – 18	Satisfactory
11 – 14	Fairly satisfactory
10 and below	Did not meet expectation

Interpretation Guide for Over-all performance of the respondents in Pre-test and Post-test in Reading

SCORES	VERBAL DESCRIPTIONS
6	Excellent
5	Outstanding
4	Very satisfactory
3	Satisfactory
2	Fairly satisfactory
1	Poor
0	Did not meet expectation

Verbal interpretation to describe the performance of the students in Reading Test that consisted of six items in each skill

Paired t-test: This statistical tool was used to test whether there is a significant difference in the performance of the students in the pre-test and post-test. Using the 0.05 level of significance as gauge, p value lower than the set criteria was decided as rejected null hypothesis thus, interpreted as significant. This treatment answered the research question number 2.

Standard Deviation. This tool measured the dispersion of the pre-test and post-test scores as well learning gains of the respondents. This is also used to determine the position of the scores in a frequency distribution in relation to the mean.

Learning Gain. These statistics aimed to determine the skill increment based on the difference between pretest and post test scores of the respondents and divided by the difference between the maximum score obtained and the pretest performance. The pre- assessment and post assessment correspond to the raw score in pretest and posttest respectively (Emporia State University, 2006). The leaning gain of the students were computed to determine which among the competency has the highest increment and the least as well. This treatment answered the statement of the problem no. 3. The formula used was:

$$learning\ gain = \frac{post\ assessment - pre\ assessment}{total\ number\ of\ items - pre\ assessment}$$

On the other hand, the qualitative data was analyzed using Thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is first developed by Gerald Holton in 1970s and has recently been accepted as a “distinctive method with a clearly outlined set of procedures in social

science” (Braun & Clarke, 2013). According to these authors, thematic analysis is a data analysis method that helps a researcher to identify themes and patterns of meanings across a dataset in relation to a research question(s). They further state that this method can be used to analyze almost any kind of qualitative data such as interviews, focus groups, and qualitative surveys, using larger or smaller datasets. By employing this data analysis method, the researcher can capture complex, messy, and contradictory relationships that prevail in the real world. However, it is exciting and enriching as well as challenging (Attride-Stirling, 2001; Braun & Clarke, 2013;) because qualitative research can identify relationships and patterns emerging from the data and by doing so, the researcher can contribute to a particular domain of knowledge by locating the study findings within existing knowledge and if possible, by challenging them.

This data analysis method enabled the researcher to identify commonly recognized patterns and relationships to meaningfully answer the research questions of the study. According to Braun and Clarke (2013), this method involves seven steps: transcription, reading and familiarization, coding, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining, and naming themes, and finalizing the analysis.

Results and Discussion

The results of the study on the use of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) in Improving the Reading Skills of Grade 12 of Paliparan II Integrated High School are presented as follows:

Score	Description	Drawing Conclusions		Summarizing		Noting Details		Making Inferences		Forming Generalization	
		f	%	F	%	F	%	f	%	F	%
6	Excellent	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
5	Outstanding	0	0.00	1	2.86	4	11.43	4	11.43	0	0.00
4	Very Satisfactory	3	8.57	1	2.86	10	28.57	8	22.86	4	11.43
3	Satisfactory	8	22.86	10	28.57	12	34.29	14	40.00	12	34.29
2	Fairly Satisfactory	12	34.29	15	42.86	8	22.86	6	17.14	10	28.57
1	Poor	8	22.86	5	14.29	1	2.86	3	8.57	7	20.00
0	Did Not Meet Expectation	4	11.43	3	8.57	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	5.71
Total		35	100.00	35	100.00	35	100.00	35	100.00	35	100.00
Mean		1.94 (FS)		2.11 (FS)		3.23 (S)		2.14 (FS)		2.26 (FS)	
SD		1.14		1.08		1.03		1.09		1.09	

Table 1. Pre-Test Performance in Reading by Competency

Table 1 shows the pre-test performance of the respondents in reading by competency. In the pre-test, competencies which were tested are drawing conclusions, summarizing, noting details, making inferences, and forming generalization. There are six questions formulated in each competency.

In the drawing conclusion test, the mean performance of respondents in is 1.94 and described as fairly satisfactory and a standard deviation of 1.14. This skill in reading requires the students to look for information that is implied or inferred. This means that the information is never clearly stated. Students need to read between the lines since most of the writers often tell you more than they say directly.

In terms of summarizing, the mean performance of the respondents in pre-test is 2.11 which fairly satisfactory with a standard deviation of 1.08. This suggest that reading is done through taking large selections of text and reduces them, making sure to include the main points and the general idea of the article (Jones, 2012). The purpose of this skill in is to require students to pull out the main ideas out of the passage and focus on the key details.

Moreover, in terms of noting details, it can be inferred in the table that no one among the 35 respondents answered the six questions for noting details. The mean performance of the students in noting details is 3.23 which is described as

satisfactory with a standard deviation of 1.03. This skill enables the reader to fully understand if a certain text and helps to unlock the questions before, during, and after reading. Noting details is a factual type of reading comprehension in which the reader is directly concerned with remembering items within the passage. Furthermore, in making inferences, the mean performance of the respondents is 2.14 which is fairly satisfactory with a standard deviation of 1.09. Making an inference involves using what you know to make a guess about what the reader do not know or reading between the lines. Readers who make inferences use the clues in the text along with their own experiences to help them figure out what is not directly said, making the text personal and memorable. Lastly, with regard to forming generalization, the mean performance of the students in forming generalization is 2.26 which is fairly satisfactory with a standard deviation of 1.09. A generalization is a broad statement that describes a situation in terms of what is generally true. Most generalizations are used to connect different facts about the same situation or topic. Generalizations are statements that may include or imply ideas. Thoughtful readers can recognize generalizations. This skill allows students to evaluate if a generalization is adequately supported by specific facts.

Score	Description	Drawing Conclusions		Summarizing		Noting Details		Making Inferences		Forming Generalization	
		F	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	F	%
6	Excellent	1	2.86	8	22.86	16	45.71	5	14.29	3	8.57
5	Outstanding	18	51.43	12	34.29	12	34.29	9	25.71	15	42.86
4	Very Satisfactory	13	37.14	11	31.43	6	17.14	20	57.14	10	28.57
3	Satisfactory	3	8.57	4	11.43	1	2.86	1	2.86	7	20.00
2	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
1	Poor	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
0	Did Not Meet Expectation	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total		35	100.00	35	100.00	35	100.00	35	100.00	35	100.00
Mean		4.54 (O)		4.69 (O)		5.20 (O)		4.49 (VS)		4.40 (VS)	
SD		0.74		0.96		0.83		0.78		0.91	

Table 2: Post-Test Performance in Reading by Competency

Table 2 divulges the performance of the students in the post- test in reading by competency. The test was administered after the full implementation of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) in the lesson plan.

In terms of Drawing conclusion, the results posit that majority of the respondents are outstanding during the post-test with a mean of 4.54 which is outstanding and standard deviation of 0.74. It can be noted that after the exposure of the respondents on Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) their performance in drawing conclusion has increased. The essence of CORI method is integration of content which has served as reading engagement promoter. Students' performance in drawing conclusion increased using the concept as a springboard in enhancing the skill. There are sets of questions constructed out of the topic that prompted the students to make judgement out of the learned concept and this help the students to read between the lines.

On the other hand, the results suggest that in **summarizing**, most of the students have an outstanding performance during the post test. This affirms the performance of the respondents has a mean of 4.69 and standard deviation of 0.96. This is associated with the primary aim of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) which had evidently reflective to performance of the respondents in summarizing since the concepts from other discipline was processed in the discussion and students are required to pull out the main ideas out of the passage and focus on the key details. Respondents were required to summarize the sample text after discussing the content.

In addition, it can be noted in the performance of the respondents in posttest reading particularly in **noting details** that majority got a perfect score which is 6. The mean score of the respondents is 5.20 and the standard deviation is 0.83. Performance of the students in this skill has increased after the utilization of CORI because after reading a certain article or reading materials they are tasked to answer guide questions. This skill is done to fully understand if a certain text and helps to unlock the questions before, during, and after reading.

Similarly with the student's performance of students in **making inference**, this skill has patently increased after the use of CORI because it pays for the students to have background knowledge before making inference. Thus, knowledge that was acquired from the reading materials helped the respondents to improve their skill in making inference. The results imply that the performance of the respondents in making inferences during the post-test reading has a mean of 4.49 which is very satisfactory and a standard deviation of 0.78.

Lastly, in terms of **forming generalization**, it can be deduced in the table that the performance of the respondents in terms of forming generalization during the post-test is 4.40 which is very satisfactory and a standard deviation of 0.91. The performance of the respondents had increase after the utilization of CORI because of the activities which required the students to connect different facts about the same situation or topic. One way to synthesize, or combine, a group of facts is to form generalizations.

Competency	Computed t	Tabular t at 0.05	Description	Decision
Drawing Conclusions	9.58	2.03	Significant	Reject Ho
Summarizing	11.03	2.03	Significant	Reject Ho
Noting Details	7.62	2.03	Significant	Reject Ho
Making Inferences	9.39	2.03	Significant	Reject Ho
Forming Generalizations	8.63	2.03	Significant	Reject Ho
Over-All Performance	15.53	2.03	Significant	Reject Ho

Table 3: Test of Difference between Pre-Test and Posttest Performance in Reading

Table 3 indicates the test of difference between pre-test and post-test performance of the respondents in reading. It can be gleaned that in terms of drawing conclusion, from the tabular t at 2.03 the computed t is 9.58 which means that there is a significant difference between the performance of the respondents in pre-test and post- test, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the use of Concept oriented reading instruction significantly contributed to elevating the performance of the respondents in drawing conclusion. The same result in summarizing, from the tabular t at 2.03 and the computed t is 11.03 this suggests that there is a significant difference from the scores of the respondents during the pre-test and post-test hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Meanwhile, in noting details, the tabular t at 2.03 compared to the computed t 7.62 this suggests that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the respondents in the competency tested thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. In terms of making inference, it can be noted that the computed t which is 9.39 is higher than the tabular t which is 2.03, this implies that there is a significant difference in the performance of the respondents in making inference between the pre- and post-test. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Lastly, in terms of forming generalization, it can be seen in the table that from tabular t is 2.03 and computed t which is 8.63 this posits that there is a significant difference on the performance of the students in the pre-test and post-test, thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

The over- all performance of the respondents in the pre-test and posttest, in the computed t which is 15.53 higher than the tabular t at 2.03, this suggests that there was an increase in the reading performance of the students. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected which implies that there is a significant difference in the performance of the students in the pre-test and post-test in reading. This explains that when respondents are exposed to Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI), they perform better in the reading test. The mean has gradually increased due to the meaningful content in which the students were exposed of. This study is confirmed by Zurek (2012), in which he accentuated that to teach language skills especially reading more effectively; CORI is dubbed as most successful methods that is commonly used in Europe for many years.

Competency	Mean Learning Gains in %	Rank	SD
Drawing Conclusions	59.29	3	0.27
Summarizing	62.86	1	0.63
Noting Details	61.90	2	0.61
Making Inferences	56.95	4	0.28
Forming Generalizations	54.43	5	0.29
Over-All Performance	62.84		0.19

Table 4: Learning Gains of the students in Reading

Table 4 shows the learning gains of the respondents in reading. It can be deduced in the table that after the utilization of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction, the students demonstrated mean learning gain of 59.29 percent in drawing conclusion, 62.86 in summarizing, 61.90 percent in noting details, 56.95 percent in making inference and 54.43 percent in

forming generalization. From these results, it can be construed that the use of CORI in improving the reading skills of the respondents was effective.

The mean learning gain of the respondents had increased in percentage through the content that was used as concept promoter. Articles and authentic reading materials adapted from the different content areas were used in teaching the competencies involved in the study.

It can be deduced that the students have a better performance in summarizing as seen to have the highest percentage in learning gain. Learning gain in noting details has an almost equal in the summarizing. On the other hand, the lowest among the 5 competency was on forming generalizations. There were more students who had the wrong answers in the test. This implies that students found it difficult to form generalization since it must go with conclusions.

Theme no.	Emergent Themes
1	Increased Reading Engagement
2	Reading becomes interesting through the integration of the concepts

Table 5: Perception of Students in the Utilization of Concept Oriented Reading Instructions

Table 5 shows the themes emerged after the thorough analysis made by the researcher. One of the themes formulated is the use of Content Oriented Reading Instructions has increased Reading Engagement. Increased reading engagement has emerged as one of the themes culled from the responses of the participants. The students are cognitively active because they use strategies and seek to link the old knowledge to new information texts. In addition, the engaged reader is behaviorally active as displayed in task participation, effort, persistence in the face of difficulty, and reading frequently for pleasure and learning. The utilization of the approach emphasizes five phases of reading instruction in a content domain such as, observing and personalizing, searching, and retrieving, comprehending, and integrating, communicating to others, and interacting with peers to construct meaning. In addition, CORI can take place within the domain of any subject matter at any grade level. Lessons are developed for the express purpose of increasing student engagement. In turn, students' amount of reading increases, and ultimately, their use of reading strategies, intrinsic motivation, and achievement increase. Texts on a topic are made available to the students, and along with strategy instruction and motivational support, deep understanding of a concept develops. This shows CORI's emphasis on thematic learning. This implies that Concept Oriented Reading Instruction has positively affect the reading comprehension of students. Based on their perceptions and experiences and supported by their learning gain, the intervention is effective in improving the assessed skill.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In line with the foregoing findings, the conclusion had been drawn and encapsulated by the researcher.

1. The utilization Concept Oriented Reading Instructions is effective in augmenting the reading performance of Grade 12 students.
2. The students' performance in Reading Comprehension Skills displayed a significant difference between the results of pre-test and post-test. This supported the claims that the utilization of Concept Oriented Reading Instructions contributes on the enhanced results in the Reading Comprehensions of the students.
3. The respondents achieved significantly higher in their score upon the utilization of the Concept Oriented Reading Instructions. This was supported by the learning gains, and the students' increment in performance from pretest to posttest. Hence, this proved that collaborative close reading is effective in enhancing Literary Analysis Writing Skills.
4. It was also concluded that students Increased Reading Engagement and Reading becomes interesting through the integration of the concepts.

Implications

The use of Content Oriented Reading Instruction (CORI) has significantly improved the reading skills of students. The approach is based on the belief that reading skills can be developed through a variety of strategies and concepts taught together. Moreover, it is a teaching method that defines reading engagement as, "the interplay of motivation, conceptual knowledge, strategies, and social interaction during literacy activities. Furthermore, it fostered reading engagement and comprehension through the teaching of reading strategies, teaching of scientific concepts and inquiry skills, and its explicit support of the development of student intrinsic motivation to read.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Basco, M.R (2020) Correlation Between Tributaries and Performance in three macro skills in English. University of the Philippines
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2013). Successful qualitative research: A practical guide for beginners. SAGE Publications. (CORI) to improve teaching and learning of reading narrative texts to the eighth grade students of SMP Ma'arifTegalSambiJepara in academic year 2013/2014. Journal English Language Teaching (ELT) Volume 1 Nomor 1, Maret 2015
- Damasali (2021) on Reading Performance of Senior High School students. The National Teachers College
- Jones, R. (2012). Strategies for reading comprehension: Summarizing. Reading Quest.
- Kalsum, U. (2018). The Effect Of Concept Oriented Reading Instruction (Cori) Strategy Toward Students' Reading Comprehension. Journal of Applied Linguistics and Literature
- Nailatun, J. (2014). The effect of the use of Concept-Oriented Reading Instruction
- Seyed, M. E. (2010). Language In India:Some Gaps In The Current Studies of Reading In Second/Foreign Language Learning
- Snow, M.A.2001.Content-based and immersion models for second and foreign teaching. In M. Celce-Murcia (Ed.),Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language (3rd ed.)(pp.303- 318).Boston, MA: Heinie&Heinie. [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234765555_Concept Oriented_Reading_Instruction_Engaging_Classrooms_Lifelong_Learners_Solving_Problems_in_the_Teaching_of_Literacy](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234765555_Concept_Oriented_Reading_Instruction_Engaging_Classrooms_Lifelong_Learners_Solving_Problems_in_the_Teaching_of_Literacy)
- Tingson, J., & Aquino, J. (2021). Addressing Reading Comprehension Difficulties in Printed Modular Distance Learning: A Case Study. *International Journal of English Language Studies*. <https://www.readingrockets.org/article/overview-concept-oriented-reading-instruction-cori>
- Zurek, O. (2012). Teaching mathematics through English Mathematics as a CORI subject. Palacky University Olomuc. Faculty of Education.Department of English

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.